

Natural products targeting *Candida auris*: A pharmaceutical review

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Abstract

Candida auris is an emerging, multidrug-resistant yeast that can cause severe and sometimes fatal infections. A literature search of the Web of Science, Scopus, and PubMed databases identified natural products from plant, microbial, and animal sources. These agents have shown varying degrees of activity against *C. auris*, ranging from growth inhibition to biofilm prevention or disruption. The effects also include reductions in virulence-related traits and interference with stress-associated and resistance responses. Semisynthetic modification and drug delivery formulations have also been reported to improve compound solubility and stability and to support *in vivo* evaluation. Moreover, the current evidence for the majority of the natural products covered in this review is based solely on *in vitro* experiments; hence, extensive pharmacokinetic and toxicological evaluation, as well as valid *in vivo* studies, are required.

Keywords

antibiofilm, anticandidal, antifungal, multidrug-resistant fungi, natural compounds, secondary metabolites

Introduction

Candida auris (*C. auris*) is an emerging, multidrug-resistant yeast posing a global threat to human health. Numerous *C. auris* outbreaks and patient infections have been reported in hospitals, intensive care units (ICUs), and long-term care facilities (LTCFs) since it was first identified as an emerging *Candida* species (Chowdhary et al. 2017). Outbreaks of *C. auris* are difficult to control because this species can survive for weeks on dry abiotic surfaces, is resistant to many disinfectants, and appears to spread readily within healthcare settings (Welsh et al. 2017; Rutala et al. 2019). The most commonly reported clinical manifestation of *C. auris* is candidemia, although deep-seated and device-associated infections have been reported and are associated with high mortality (Calvo et

al. 2016; Chowdhary et al. 2017). Most *C. auris* strains are reported to be resistant to at least one class of antifungal agents, with fluconazole resistance common, along with increasing reports of resistance to amphotericin B and echinocandins (Lamoth and Kontoyiannis 2018; Lyman et al. 2021). Several resistance mechanisms have been identified, including target mutations, adaptive aneuploidy, clade-specific changes in gene expression, and alterations in lipid synthesis (Bing et al. 2021). Experimental evolution studies have shown that *C. auris* adaptive aneuploidy is a key mechanism of azole resistance (Bing et al. 2021). A combined transcriptomic and multi-omics study has shown increased levels of oxidative stress following exposure to amphotericin B, as well as changes in sterol and sphingolipid biosynthesis, consistent with mechanisms of amphotericin B resistance (Chaabane et al. 2019; Chau-

han et al. 2025). Recent work indicates that *PDR16* gene dosage modulates antifungal susceptibility in *C. auris*, with the clearest effect observed for azoles (Phan-Canh et al. 2025). PTR-family transporters, particularly Ptr-C, have been implicated in the uptake of peptide substrates and peptide-based antifungal agents in *C. auris*, indicating a potential role in antifungal delivery rather than a demonstrated role in stress resilience (Khattoon et al. 2025). Hence, therapeutic failure is common, particularly in biofilm-associated infections, where *C. auris* has been shown to exhibit reduced susceptibility compared with its planktonic counterparts. Biofilm formation on indwelling devices is a key factor for the persistence of the fungus on these devices and is associated with reduced drug penetration and tolerance to antifungal drugs (Dominguez et al. 2019; Romera et al. 2019). Combination therapy, such as echinocandin–azole combinations, and dosing optimization, including pharmacokinetic–pharmacodynamic approaches to optimize echinocandin exposure in critically ill patients, are therefore active areas of investigation (Fakhim et al. 2017; Watcharasuwanseree et al. 2025).

Natural products remain a key source of structurally diverse scaffolds for developing new agents against opportunistic fungi, including *C. auris*. In this context, research on natural products targeting *C. auris* has focused on plant- and microorganism-derived secondary metabolites (Zhang et al. 2020; Zhao et al. 2021) and selected animal-derived molecules (Wani et al. 2024). Across these studies, natural products and their semisynthetic derivatives were assessed for antifungal activity against planktonic cells and biofilms, as well as for their effects on *C. auris* virulence-associated traits (Zhang et al. 2020; Kovács et al. 2021; Zhao et al. 2021; Retore et al. 2024; Usui et al. 2025). There is a growing number of studies evaluating these molecules in combination with existing antifungal drugs such as azoles, echinocandins, and polyenes (Zhang et al. 2020; Kovács et al. 2021; Zhao et al. 2021; Retore et al. 2024; Usui et al. 2025). Moreover, formulation-oriented approaches inspired by natural-product research, including liposomal systems, nanostructured lipid carriers, and polymer-based nanoparticles, have been investigated primarily to address challenges related to stability, solubility, and delivery (Zhao et al. 2021; Retore et al. 2024; Usui et al. 2025). This review systematically compiles and evaluates natural products and natural-product-derived agents reported to exhibit activity against *C. auris*, with emphasis on biological source, chemical identity, experimental assay context, antibiofilm and anti-virulence outcomes, interactions with currently approved antifungals, and translational considerations such as selectivity, stability, and suitability for further pharmaceutical development.

Methods and search strategy

A structured literature search was conducted across PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science to identify publications examining biological activities against *C. auris*. The

search terms were selected to capture studies reporting susceptibility testing, antifungal activity, fungicidal and fungistatic effects, biofilm disruption and eradication, and compound interactions, including synergy, additivity, and antagonism. These terms were specific to the pathogen and to the biological characteristics and experimental readouts commonly used to evaluate natural product activity. The search terms for the individual databases are provided in Suppl. material 1: table S1 and were consistent across all databases, except for database-specific field labels, which were applied without modifying the core search terms.

A total of 1,455 records were retrieved from PubMed, 1,575 from Web of Science, and 1,604 from Scopus, generating 4,634 records prior to deduplication. After removing duplicate records, 1,921 unique records remained for further assessment. Titles and abstracts were screened to identify studies relevant to natural products or natural product derivatives. Irrelevant records, such as studies focusing solely on synthetic compounds, as well as those addressing epidemiology, clinical surveillance, or diagnostic methods, were excluded based on predefined criteria. A total of 195 records were retained for full-text evaluation based on their relevance to natural products or natural product derivatives. A high proportion of the retained studies examined the activity of natural products or their derivatives against *C. auris*, by evaluating planktonic growth susceptibility, assessing biofilm-inhibitory activity, or testing combinations with existing antifungal agents. Studies included in this review reported *in vitro* susceptibility, antibiofilm, or anti-virulence effects and, in many cases, provided insight into mechanisms of action or included *in vivo* models such as catheter-associated infection, skin colonization, or insect-based infection systems. Studies were excluded if species-level identification of *C. auris* was unclear, the structure of the active compound or compounds was not defined, or experimental methods and outcomes were insufficiently described.

The present review focuses on natural products, defined as chemically characterized bioactive substances of biological origin, including isolated secondary metabolites and chemically defined mixtures derived from natural sources. Semisynthetic derivatives of natural scaffolds and natural product-inspired structural analogues were included within the derivative category. The included studies were categorized according to biological origin, as depicted in Fig. 1, into plant-derived natural products, including pure compounds and chemically characterized plant extracts, microbial-derived natural products, including secondary metabolites, lipopeptides, proteins, and postbiotic products, and animal-derived natural products, including antimicrobial peptides and other bioactive animal-derived substances. Studies involving natural product-derived leads, natural product use in combination strategies, and formulation approaches were grouped under pharmaceutical development strategies for anti-*Candida auris* natural products. This classification was applied consistently to facilitate comparison of study design and reported antifungal outcomes across categories.

Figure 1. Classification of natural products reported to exhibit antifungal or antibiofilm activity against *Candida auris* according to biological origin.

Natural products active against *C. auris*

Natural products reported to exhibit activity against *C. auris* involve a wide range of chemical scaffolds, including phenolics (Rossatto et al. 2021), terpenoids (Usui et al. 2025), quinones (de Moraes et al. 2024), polyketide-like scaffolds (Singh et al. 2024a), lipopeptides (Ramachandran et al. 2018), antimicrobial peptides (Raber et al. 2021), and other structurally diverse bioactive molecules (Basso et al. 2018; Honorato et al. 2024). These chemical classes were obtained from plant-, microbial-, and animal-based sources. Despite this diversity, reported biological effects converge on a set of recurring outcomes, most prominently inhibition of planktonic growth, suppression or disruption of biofilms, attenuation of adhesion and virulence-associated traits, cell wall perturbation, modulation of cellular stress responses, and potentiation of standard antifungal drug activity in combination settings (Fig. 2).

Plant-derived natural products

Plant-derived agents evaluated against *C. auris* comprise purified small molecules, peptide-based defenses, standardized extracts, and essential oils. These studies report inhibition of planktonic growth, interference with biofilm development, modulation of virulence-associated traits, and, in some cases, resistance-modifying effects. However, the degree of chemical definition, mechanistic depth, and

translational relevance varies substantially across compound classes. A comprehensive table of key chemically defined plant-derived antifungal leads, plant extracts, and essential oils is provided in Suppl. material 1: table S2.

Phenolic compounds, tannins, naphthoquinones, and phenolic-rich botanical extracts

Phenolic compounds constitute one of the most extensively investigated classes of plant-derived antifungal agents evaluated against *C. auris*. Within this group, ellagic acid has been examined using standardized planktonic broth microdilution assays, in which it demonstrated measurable growth inhibition of *C. auris* and prolonged the survival of *Galleria mellonella* infected with *C. auris* (Rossatto et al. 2021). The study reported direct antifungal activity and prolonged survival in *Galleria mellonella*, while mechanistic evidence more specifically suggests alteration of the fungal cell wall rather than a clearly established redox- or membrane-centered mode of action (Rossatto et al. 2021). Although these effects are consistent with the known physicochemical properties of polyphenols, the available evidence primarily supports proof-of-concept antifungal activity rather than target-specific inhibition (Rossatto et al. 2021). Hydrolysable tannins represent a structurally more complex subclass of phenolic compounds with enhanced multivalent binding capacity. Penta-O-galloyl- β -D-glucose, a highly galloylated glucose derivative, demonstrated *in vitro* growth inhibition of *C. auris*, as well as other *Candida* species, high-

Figure 2. Biological effects of natural products evaluated against *Candida auris*.

lighting the antifungal potential of dense galloyl substitution patterns that may promote interactions with fungal cell wall proteins and membrane components (Marquez et al. 2023). Similarly, tannic acid, a broadly distributed plant tannin, exhibited planktonic antifungal activity against *C. auris* and suppressed selected virulence-associated phenotypes in mechanistic assays (Ríos-López et al. 2024). The findings indicate biological effects that extend beyond simple fungistatic growth inhibition and may involve modulation of pathogenic traits. These observations support the concept that polyphenolic compounds can interfere with *C. auris* viability and pathogenicity. However, translational relevance remains constrained by limitations in bioavailability, nonspecific protein binding, and potential host toxicity (Marquez et al. 2023; Ríos-López et al. 2024).

Naphthoquinones constitute a chemically distinct subset of phenolic-derived small molecules with defined intracellular targets. For example, β -lapachone exhibited antifungal activity against fluconazole-resistant *C. auris*, inhibiting planktonic growth, preventing biofilm formation, and reducing the metabolic activity of preformed biofilms (de Moraes et al. 2024). Mechanistic investigations employing fluorescent probes and biochemical assays revealed disruption of cell wall chitin content, alterations in neutral lipid composition, and loss of mitochondrial membrane integrity, indicating a multifaceted mode of action involving both structural and metabolic stress (de Moraes et al. 2024). Notably, combination studies did not demonstrate synergistic interactions with fluconazole or amphotericin B, suggesting that β -lapachone may be better positioned as a direct-acting lead rather than an adjuvant antifungal. Plumbagin, a plant-derived naphthoqui-

none, showed notable antifungal and antibiofilm activity against *C. auris*, including inhibition of biofilm formation and reduction of mature-biofilm metabolic activity (Jin and Eom 2025). The study also reported downregulation of *ERG11*, *CDR1*, and *KRE6*, supporting effects on ergosterol-associated pathways, drug-response machinery, and cell-wall-related processes. Because plumbagin is a naphthoquinone, these findings should nevertheless be interpreted cautiously in translational terms, since quinone scaffolds may combine antifungal activity with broad redox reactivity and potential host-cell toxicity (Bolton et al. 2000). The plant-derived phenolic compounds, tannins, and naphthoquinones evaluated against *C. auris* are summarized in Table 1.

In parallel with purified phenolic compounds, several phenolic-rich botanical extracts and plant-derived preparations have been evaluated against *C. auris* by planktonic susceptibility assays, often supplemented with targeted mechanistic readouts. A phenolic-rich leaf extract of *Eugenia uniflora* inhibited *C. auris* growth *in vitro*, and complementary *in silico* analyses suggested potential molecular interactions with fungal targets (Machado et al. 2025). However, the experimental antifungal evidence remains fundamentally based on broth microdilution, supported by mechanistic inference rather than direct target validation. Similarly, preparations derived from *Caryocar brasiliense* inhibited multidrug-resistant *C. auris* in planktonic assays (Retore et al. 2024). They were further evaluated in combination studies, in which enhanced activity was observed with selected conventional antifungals, suggesting potential relevance for adjunctive strategies. Additional plant extracts from *Plantago major* (Sousa et al. 2025b), characterized by phenolics and iridoids, and

Table 1. Phenolic acids, tannins, and naphthoquinones evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Source	Chemical class	Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
Ellagic acid	Representative sources include <i>Punica granatum</i> , <i>Terminalia chebula</i> , and <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Phenolic acid	Broth microdilution assay, MIC 0.125 to 0.25 µg/mL	Showed growth inhibition of <i>C. auris</i> , associated with an effect on the fungal cell wall	Rossatto et al. 2021
Penta-O-galloyl-β-D-glucose	Representative sources include <i>Paeonia suffruticosa</i> , <i>Rhus chinensis</i> , and <i>Punica granatum</i>	Hydrolysable tannin	MIC determination assay, MIC 0.25 to 8 µg/mL	Showed inhibitory activity against <i>C. auris</i> isolates across a broad concentration range	Marquez et al. 2023
Tannic acid	Representative sources include <i>Quercus infectoria</i> , <i>Caesalpinia spinosa</i> , and <i>Camellia sinensis</i>	Hydrolysable tannin	MIC and virulence assays, MIC 8 µg/mL	Showed growth inhibition and suppression of virulence-associated traits in <i>C. auris</i>	Ríos-López et al. 2024
β-Lapachone	<i>Handroanthus impetiginosus</i>	Naphthoquinone	Broth microdilution and biofilm assays, planktonic growth inhibition 92.7% at 100 µg/mL; biofilm formation inhibition 84.9% at 100 µg/mL; preformed biofilm metabolism reduction 87.1% at 100 µg/mL	Showed inhibition of planktonic growth and biofilms, with disruption of mitochondrial function and cell wall integrity	de Moraes et al. 2024
Plumbagin	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Naphthoquinone	Broth microdilution and biofilm assays, MIC 1 to 4 µg/mL; approximately 80% inhibition of biofilm formation and reduction of pre-formed biofilm at 2 µg/mL	Showed antifungal and antibiofilm activity, supported by CLSM and associated with downregulation of <i>ERG11</i> , <i>CDR1</i> , and <i>KRE6</i>	Jin and Eom 2025

Thunbergia alata (Romero et al. 2023), containing mixed secondary metabolites, also demonstrated planktonic growth inhibition of *C. auris* in broth microdilution assays. While such studies broaden the repertoire of plant-derived candidates beyond purified compounds, their translational interpretability remains dependent on extract standardization, definition of chemical markers, and reproducibility across batches and chemotypes.

Phenylpropanoids, terpenoids, and essential oils

Phenylpropanoids and terpenoid-derived compounds, evaluated either as isolated molecules or as dominant constituents of essential oils, constitute a major class of plant-derived agents investigated against *C. auris*. Caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE), a phenylpropanoid ester, inhibited *C. auris* growth in planktonic assays and reduced adhesion, biofilm formation, and hemolytic activity (Rossatto et al. 2021). The study supports the possibility of effects on the fungal cell wall. These observations are consistent with the established bioactivity of phenylpropanoid esters, which typically exert antifungal effects by disrupting membranes and inducing oxidative stress rather than through highly specific molecular targets (Alfarayeh et al. 2021). Cinnamaldehyde, a phenylpropanoid aldehyde abundant in *Cinnamomum* species, demonstrated fungicidal activity against planktonic *C. auris* in broth microdilution assays (Sousa et al. 2025a). Proteomic analyses implicated disruption of ergosterol biosynthesis pathways; however, cytotoxicity was observed at concentrations associated with antifungal activity, raising concerns regarding therapeutic selectivity and safety margins.

In contrast, eugenol, another phenylpropanoid, exhibited fungicidal activity against multiple clinical *C. auris* isolates without detectable cytotoxicity at active concentrations (Sousa et al. 2025a). Beyond direct fungicidal activity, eugenol-associated antibiofilm effects have also been linked to impaired adhesion, which is particularly relevant for *C. auris* because surface attachment contributes to its persistence on medical and hospital-associated surfaces (Shahina and Dahms 2024). Proteomic profiling similarly suggested interference with sterol metabolism, indicating a more favorable balance between antifungal efficacy and host cell tolerance. Among terpenoid compounds, carvacrol and geraniol have been examined in greater mechanistic detail. Carvacrol inhibited *C. auris* growth in planktonic assays and induced oxidative stress, as evidenced by increased lipid peroxidation and upregulation of antioxidant enzyme activity and gene expression, consistent with redox-mediated antifungal mechanisms (Ismail et al. 2022). Geraniol displayed fungicidal activity against multidrug-resistant *C. auris*, accompanied by inhibition of ABC efflux pump activity, depletion of ergosterol, suppression of biofilm formation, and enhanced clearance in a *Caenorhabditis elegans* infection model, highlighting its relevance beyond *in vitro* susceptibility testing (Fatima et al. 2023). Table 2 shows selected plant-derived phenylpropanoids and terpenoids reported to exhibit activity against *C. auris*.

Essential oils represent a promising class of natural antifungal agents, with applications extending beyond clinical therapeutics to food preservation and surface disinfection due to their broad-spectrum antimicrobial properties (Ivanova et al. 2025). However, unlike other classes of natural products discussed in this review, the

Table 2. Phenylpropanoids and terpenoids evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Source	Chemical class	Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
Caffeic acid phenethyl ester, CAPE	Representative sources include propolis and <i>Baccharis dracunculifolia</i>	Phenylpropanoid ester	Broth microdilution and biofilm assays, MIC 1 to 64 µg/mL	Showed antifungal and anti-virulence activity, including reduction of biofilm biomass, biofilm metabolic activity, and adhesion	Rossatto et al. 2021
Cinnamaldehyde	Representative source: <i>Cinnamomum verum</i> bark oil	Phenylpropanoid aldehyde	Broth microdilution assay, fungicidal activity at 31.25 to 250 µg/mL	Showed fungicidal activity, likely involving ergosterol biosynthesis, but cytotoxicity was detected at active concentrations	Sousa et al. 2025a
Eugenol	Representative sources include <i>Syzygium aromaticum</i> , <i>Ocimum basilicum</i> , and <i>Cinnamomum verum</i> leaf oil	Phenylpropanoid	Broth microdilution assay, fungicidal activity at 31.25 to 250 µg/mL	Showed fungicidal activity, likely involving ergosterol biosynthesis, with no detectable cytotoxicity at growth-inhibitory concentrations	Sousa et al. 2025a
Carvacrol	Representative sources include <i>Origanum vulgare</i> and <i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	Monoterpenoid phenol	Microdilution assay, MIC 125 to 500 µg/mL	Showed growth inhibition, associated with oxidative stress, increased antioxidant enzyme activity and expression, and lipid peroxidation	Ismail et al. 2022
Geraniol	Representative sources include <i>Cymbopogon martinii</i> and <i>Pelargonium graveolens</i>	Monoterpenoid alcohol	Broth microdilution and biofilm assays, MIC 225 µg/mL	Showed fungicidal activity, efflux pump inhibition, ergosterol depletion, inhibition of biofilm formation, and <i>in vivo</i> efficacy	Fatima et al. 2023

antifungal activity of essential oils against *C. auris* has been evaluated almost exclusively *in vitro*. *In vivo* validation remains very limited, with available evidence largely restricted to non-mammalian models or combination-based studies rather than well-developed stand-alone mammalian evaluations of specific essential oils against *C. auris*. Essential oils rich in phenylpropanoids and terpenoids have been widely evaluated due to their multicomponent composition and broad biological activity. For example, *Thymus* oils exhibited antifungal and antibiofilm activity against *C. auris*, with substantial variability depending on botanical source and chemotype (Ribeiro et al. 2022). Activity correlated strongly with monoterpenoid content, particularly thymol and carvacrol, and was observed in both direct-contact and vapor-phase exposure models (Ribeiro et al. 2022). Cinnamon leaf and bark essential oils from *Cinnamomum verum* demonstrated potent antifungal activity, with bark oil consistently outperforming leaf oil (Tran et al. 2020). This difference is plausibly attributable to the distinct chemical profiles of the two oils, since bark oil is enriched in cinnamaldehyde, whereas leaf oil contains a higher proportion of eugenol, indicating that antifungal potency within *Cinnamomum* preparations depends strongly on the dominant constituent and plant part (Tran et al. 2020; Sousa et al. 2025a). Reported effects included membrane damage, inhibition of hyphal development, and reduced hemolytic activity. Essential oil from *Cinnamomum cassia* similarly exhibited fungistatic and fungicidal activity against planktonic and biofilm-associated *C. auris* (Rosato et al. 2023). In addition, *Lavandula angustifolia* essential oil inhibited planktonic growth and eradicated both primary and persister-derived *C. auris* biofilms, with mechanistic evidence linking activity to intracellular reactive oxygen species accumulation and transcriptional modulation of stress-response, efflux, and ergosterol-as-

sociated genes (Alteriis et al. 2022). To facilitate comparison across studies, selected essential oils evaluated specifically against *C. auris* are summarized in Table 3.

Peptides and steroidal metabolites

Beyond small-molecule secondary metabolites, structurally distinct antifungal agents of plant origin have also been reported against *C. auris*. A plant-derived defensin-like protein, D-lp1, exhibited antifungal activity against clinical *C. auris* isolates, with minimum inhibitory concentration and minimum fungicidal concentration values ranging from 0.047 to 0.78 µg/mL and 0.095 to 1.56 µg/mL, respectively (Kamli et al. 2022). In addition to inhibiting planktonic growth, D-lp1 markedly suppressed biofilm formation and reduced mature biofilms at subinhibitory concentrations, indicating activity against both planktonic and biofilm-associated fungal populations. Mechanistic assays demonstrated disruption of fungal membrane integrity and attenuation of virulence-associated traits, while hemolysis testing revealed minimal activity against mammalian erythrocytes, supporting a favorable selectivity profile (Kamli et al. 2022). Collectively, these findings indicate that D-lp1 acts as a multifunctional antifungal agent with planktonic, antibiofilm, and anti-virulence effects.

In addition to peptide-based agents, structurally specialized plant-derived small molecules have also shown antifungal activity against *C. auris*. A steroidal natural product isolated from *Tephrosia apollinea* and named TNS exhibited concentration-dependent inhibition of *C. auris* in planktonic assays, with activity becoming more pronounced at higher concentrations and reaching approximately 90% inhibition at 700 to 900 µg/mL (Ashmawy et al. 2022). The crude methanol extract showed only weak inhibition, remaining below 15% even at the highest test-

Table 3. Essential oils evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Plant part	Chemical class	*Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
<i>Thymus vulgaris</i> essential oil	Aerial parts	Monoterpenoid-rich essential oil	Agar disk diffusion and biofilm CFU assays, inhibition zone diameter 42.33 ± 3.77 mm	Showed the highest antifungal activity among the tested <i>Thymus</i> species, with stronger antibiofilm activity in direct application and significant vapor-phase activity	Ribeiro et al. 2022
<i>Thymus zygis</i> essential oil	Aerial parts	Monoterpenoid-rich essential oil	Agar disk diffusion and biofilm CFU assays, inhibition zone diameter 28.25 ± 1.09 mm	Showed the second-highest antifungal activity, with a greater antibiofilm effect in direct application than in vapor phase	Ribeiro et al. 2022
<i>Thymus satureioides</i> essential oil	Aerial parts	Monoterpenoid-rich essential oil	Agar disk diffusion and biofilm CFU assays, inhibition zone diameter 20.00 ± 0.63 mm	Showed lower antifungal and antibiofilm activity than <i>T. vulgaris</i> and <i>T. zygis</i>	Ribeiro et al. 2022
<i>Thymus mastichina</i> essential oil	Aerial parts	Linalool-rich essential oil	Agar disk diffusion and biofilm CFU assays, inhibition zone diameter 13.60 ± 1.36 mm	Showed the lowest antifungal activity among the tested <i>Thymus</i> species	Ribeiro et al. 2022
<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> bark oil	Bark	Phenylpropanoid-rich essential oil	Broth microdilution and diffusion assays, MIC $<0.03\%$ v/v, MFC $<0.03\%$ v/v	Showed greater antifungal activity than leaf oil, associated with membrane damage and reduction of hemolytic activity	Tran et al. 2020
<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> leaf oil	Leaf	Phenylpropanoid-rich essential oil	Broth microdilution and diffusion assays, MIC 0.06% v/v, MFC 0.25% v/v	Showed antifungal activity with lower potency than bark oil, associated with membrane damage and reduction of hemolytic activity	Tran et al. 2020
<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> essential oil	Bark	Phenylpropanoid-rich essential oil	Broth microdilution and preformed biofilm assays, average MIC $0.01 \pm 0.01\%$ v/v, average MFC $0.01 \pm 0.01\%$ v/v; biofilm disruption at 0.02% v/v	Showed fungistatic and fungicidal activity against planktonic cells and significant disruption of pre-formed biofilm	Rosato et al. 2023
<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> essential oil	Aerial parts	Terpenoid-rich essential oil	Planktonic and biofilm assays, planktonic growth reduction from 0.01% v/v; primary and persister-derived biofilm eradication $>80\%$ at 0.5% v/v	Showed eradication of primary and persister-derived biofilms, increased intracellular ROS, and modulation of <i>ERG11</i> , <i>ALS5</i> , <i>HOG1</i> , and <i>CDR1</i>	Alteriis et al. 2022

*Disk diffusion assays were performed using 10 μ L essential oil per 6 mm paper disk.

ed concentration. The purified compound showed limited cytotoxicity at lower concentrations, but cytotoxicity increased with increasing doses. Steroidal scaffolds occupy a distinct chemical space in antifungal research, since they may interact with lipid membranes and sterol-dependent pathways while retaining the potential for selective molecular recognition. In the same study, *in silico* molecular docking and homology modeling supported the experimental findings by identifying plausible interactions with fungal targets and providing a structure-based rationale for the observed antifungal activity (Ashmawy et al. 2022).

Microbial-derived natural products

Microorganisms constitute a prolific source of chemical-ly and mechanistically diverse antifungal agents, many of which have evolved to mediate intermicrobial competition within complex ecological niches. In the context of *C. auris*, microbial-derived natural products encompass small-molecule secondary metabolites, lipopeptides, proteinaceous antifungal agents, and complex postbiotic preparations derived from probiotic bacteria. Compared with many plant-derived compounds, several microbial metabolites display higher intrinsic potency, more clearly defined molecular targets, or demonstrable activity in biofilm models and *in vivo* infection systems (Rossoni et al. 2020; Zhang et al. 2020; Kovács et al. 2021; Singh

et al. 2024b). These properties support the translational relevance of microbial natural products in antifungal discovery targeting *C. auris*. The principal anti-*C. auris* microbial-derived agents reported to date are summarized in Table 4.

Small-molecule secondary metabolites

Small-molecule secondary metabolites constitute the most structurally diverse class of microbial-derived agents reported to be active against *C. auris*, encompassing polyketides, terpenoids, diketopiperazines, and hybrid scaffolds. These compounds frequently act through mechanisms distinct from those of established antifungal drug classes and, in several cases, display antibiofilm activity or synergistic interactions with standard antifungal agents. The most advanced example within this category is turbinmicin, a microbial secondary metabolite identified through microbiome-guided discovery from marine bacteria (Zhang et al. 2020; Zhao et al. 2021). Turbinmicin exhibited potent *in vitro* activity against multidrug-resistant *C. auris* and demonstrated efficacy in murine infection models. Importantly, the compound also showed a wide safety margin, with no detectable red blood cell toxicity at concentrations far exceeding the MIC and no evident toxicity in mouse dose-escalation studies. These characteristics make

Table 4. Microbial metabolites and postbiotics evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Producing organism or source	Chemical class	Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
Turbinmicin	<i>Micromonospora</i> sp. WMMC-415, isolated from the marine ascidian <i>Ecteinascidia turbinata</i>	Highly oxidized type II polyketide	Planktonic assay, MIC 0.25 µg/mL against pan-resistant <i>C. auris</i> strain B11211; fungicidal time-kill activity above the MIC; neutropenic mouse model, 0.25 to 4 µg/kg every 6 h	Showed potent activity against pan-resistant <i>C. auris</i> , no hemolytic activity at tested concentrations, with a reduction in kidney fungal burden at the highest dose	Zhang et al. 2020
Guanacastepene V and dahliane C	<i>Coprinellus xanthothrix</i>	Guanacastane-type diterpenoids	Planktonic assay, MIC 6.25 µg/mL for guanacastepene V and 3.12 µg/mL for dahliane C	Showed selective antifungal activity against <i>C. auris</i> with minimal activity against <i>C. albicans</i>	Usui et al. 2025
4-hydroxyphenylacetic acid	<i>Penicillium chrysogenum</i> wis54-1255	Phenolic acid	Planktonic assay, MIC 32 µg/mL	Showed direct antifungal activity against <i>C. auris</i>	Ji et al. 2025
Trans-1-oxo-2,4-diacetylaminodecalin (1)	<i>Streptomyces chrestomycticus</i> ADP4	Decalin derivative	Planktonic assay, concentration-dependent growth inhibition up to approximately 90% at 1000 µg/mL	Showed selective antifungal activity against <i>C. albicans</i> and <i>C. auris</i> and a favorable safety profile	Singh et al. 2024a
Diterpenic derivative, compound 55B3	<i>Streptomyces chrestomycticus</i> ADP4	Diterpenic aromatic acid derivative	Planktonic and biofilm assays, MIC ₉₀ 21.75 ± 1.5 µg/mL; MBIC ₉₀ 18.38 ± 1.78 µg/mL	Showed antifungal and antibiofilm activity against <i>C. auris</i> , inhibition of virulence-associated traits at subinhibitory concentrations, 64 ± 3% inhibition of ergosterol biosynthesis at the MIC ₉₀ , and no cytotoxicity in HepG2 cells	Singh et al. 2024b
Bacillomycin-class lipopeptide AF4	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> RLID 12.1	Cyclic lipopeptide	Planktonic assay, mean MIC 3.48 µg/mL	Showed the strongest antifungal activity among AF3, AF4, and AF5, with substantial mammalian cytotoxicity and hemolytic activity at suprainhibitory concentrations.	Ramachandran et al. 2018
NFAP2 antifungal protein	<i>Neosartorya fischeri</i>	Cysteine-rich antifungal protein	Biofilm and combination assays, 90% dead cells at 512 µg/L; median FICI 0.037 to 0.5 in combinations with conventional antifungals	Showed strong antibiofilm activity and multidrug synergy against <i>C. auris</i> biofilms	Kovács et al. 2021
Postbiotic preparation, LPCE and LPP1	<i>Lactobacillus paracasei</i> 28.4	Postbiotic metabolite mixtures	Planktonic, time-kill, biofilm, and persister-cell assays, MIC 15 µg/mL for LPCE and 3.75 to 7.5 µg/mL for LPP1; complete reduction of viable cells after 24 h	Showed reduction of biofilm biomass and metabolic activity, eradication of persister cells, and prolonged survival of infected <i>Galleria mellonella</i> larvae with associated immune stimulation	Rossoni et al. 2020
<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> Shirota, lactic acid-associated activity	<i>Lactobacillus casei</i> Shirota	Probiotic and lactic acid-dominant postbiotic activity	Coculture assay, microbicidal activity 86.6 to 93.9%; lactic acid MIC 2.5 µg/mL	Showed <i>in vitro</i> inhibition of <i>C. auris</i> growth, and activity was associated with lactic acid production	Paniagua et al. 2021

turbinmicin distinct from many other potent but less selective antifungal leads. Mechanistic studies revealed inhibition of Sec14-dependent vesicular trafficking, resulting in impaired extracellular vesicle delivery, disruption of biofilm matrix assembly, and increased susceptibility of biofilm-embedded cells. Notably, turbinmicin disrupted fungal vesicle trafficking and biofilm-associated processes and may enhance the activity of other antifungal strategies, supporting its positioning as both a direct

antifungal agent and a potential biofilm-disrupting adjuvant (Zhang et al. 2020; Zhao et al. 2021).

From *Streptomyces chrestomycticus* ADP4, a decalin-type polyketide-like compound, trans-1-oxo-2,4-diacetylaminodecalin, exhibited direct antifungal activity against *C. auris* and *C. albicans* (Singh et al. 2024a). *In silico* ADME analysis and *in vitro* HepG2 assays indicated favorable drug-likeness and an absence of detectable cytotoxicity, supporting its potential as a lead scaffold. Similar-

ly, a structurally more complex diterpenic aromatic acid derivative (compound 55B3) isolated from the same strain demonstrated potent antifungal and antibiofilm activity against *C. auris* (Singh et al. 2024b). Beyond growth inhibition, this compound suppressed virulence-associated traits, including yeast-to-hyphae transition and hydrolytic enzyme production, and significantly inhibited ergosterol biosynthesis without detectable cytotoxicity.

Fungal secondary metabolites further expand the chemical space of microbial-derived antifungal agents. Guanacastane-type diterpenoids isolated from the marine-derived fungus *Coprinellus xanthothrix* exhibited selective *in vitro* growth inhibition of *C. auris*, with minimal activity against *C. albicans*, indicating species-specific susceptibility (Usui et al. 2025). One diterpenoid displayed synergistic interaction with amphotericin B, suggesting potential utility in combination therapy rather than as a standalone agent. Likewise, chemical investigation of *Penicillium chrysogenum* metabolites identified a single indole diketopiperazine derivative with explicit anti-*C. auris* activity, while other co-isolated compounds displayed antibacterial or antioxidant effects, underscoring narrow structure–activity relationships governing antifungal specificity (Ji et al. 2025). These studies highlight microbial small-molecule secondary metabolites as a chemically diverse and mechanistically rich source of anti-*C. auris* activity, with several compounds exhibiting properties, including biofilm disruption, resistance modulation, and *in vivo* efficacy, that extend beyond conventional fungistatic effects (Zhang et al. 2020; Singh et al. 2024b; Ji et al. 2025; Usui et al. 2025).

Lipopeptides and proteinaceous antifungal agents

Lipopeptides and proteinaceous antifungal agents constitute a distinct class of microbial-derived compounds, typically characterized by membrane-active mechanisms or targeted effects on biofilm structure and integrity. Bacillomycin-class cyclic lipopeptides (AF3, AF4, and AF5), produced by *Bacillus subtilis* RLID 12.1, exhibited *in vitro* antifungal activity against *C. auris*, with AF4 achieving complete growth inhibition at 3.48 µg/mL (Ramachandran et al. 2018). Although AF4 showed strong antifungal activity, its translational potential should be interpreted cautiously because the original study also reported substantial mammalian cytotoxicity and hemolytic activity at suprainhibitory concentrations (Ramachandran et al. 2018). Proteinaceous antifungal agents of microbial origin have also shown particular value in combination-based strategies. The cysteine-rich antifungal protein NFAP2, isolated from *Neosartorya fischeri*, exhibited strong antibiofilm activity against *C. auris* and reproducible synergistic interactions with azoles, polyenes, and echinocandins (Kovács et al. 2021). Synergy was confirmed using fractional inhibitory concentration indices and Bliss independence analysis and was associated with enhanced killing of biofilm-embedded cells. These properties support the positioning of NFAP2

as an antifungal adjuvant rather than a standalone agent, particularly in the context of multidrug-resistant *C. auris* biofilm-associated infections (Kovács et al. 2021).

Postbiotic preparations and probiotic-derived antifungal activity

Complex postbiotic preparations derived from probiotic microorganisms have also demonstrated measurable antifungal activity against *C. auris*. Cell-free supernatant fractions (LPCE and LPF1) obtained from *Lactobacillus paracasei* 28.4 inhibited planktonic growth, eradicated established biofilms and persister cells, and outperformed fluconazole in time–kill assays (Rossoni et al. 2020). *In vivo* evaluation using *Galleria mellonella* infection models demonstrated improved host survival, accompanied by enhanced immune responses, indicating that these preparations may exert both direct antifungal and host-modulatory effects. Related observations were reported for *Lactobacillus casei* Shirota, which inhibited *C. auris* growth during co-cultivation experiments (Paniagua et al. 2021). In this preparation, lactic acid was identified as a principal antifungal factor, exhibiting microbicidal activity at physiologically relevant concentrations and suppressing early biofilm formation. Together, these findings indicate that postbiotic-mediated antifungal activity, driven by metabolic by-products rather than discrete secondary metabolites, may be particularly relevant for mucosal or microbiota-centered intervention strategies, where modulation of the local microbial environment contributes to pathogen control.

Animal-derived natural products and antimicrobial peptides

Animal-derived antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) and other animal-origin bioactives constitute a distinct group of agents evaluated against *C. auris*. Unlike many small-molecule antifungals, these compounds typically act by rapidly interacting with fungal membranes, resulting in rapid fungicidal effects and disruption of biofilm structure (Basso et al. 2018; Colombo et al. 2019; Wani et al. 2024). Limitations related to systemic stability and toxicity have constrained their development as systemically administered drugs; however, these same properties make them well-suited to topical applications, decolonization strategies, device coatings, and other forms of localized delivery (Basso et al. 2018; Colombo et al. 2019; Wani et al. 2024). The animal-derived peptides and peptide-inspired agents reported to exhibit antifungal or antibiofilm activity against *C. auris*, together with their assay contexts and principal outcomes, are summarized in Table 5.

Mammalian innate antimicrobial peptides and defensins

The human and primate innate immune systems encode a well-characterized repertoire of antimicrobial peptides that have attracted interest as alternative antifungal agents

Table 5. Animal-derived natural products evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Producing organism or source	Chemical class	Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
Histatin 5	Human saliva	Host-defense peptide, histatin family	Planktonic killing assay, 58 to 90% of most <i>C. auris</i> isolates' cells were killed at 22.77 µg/mL	Showed candidacidal activity against clinical <i>C. auris</i> isolates, including azole-resistant strains	Pathirana et al. 2018
θ-Defensins, including RTD-1, RTD-2, BTD-2, BTD-4, and BTD-8	Old World monkeys, specifically rhesus macaque and baboon innate immune system	Macrocyclic cysteine-rich antimicrobial peptides	Planktonic CLSI MIC/MFC assays against <i>C. auris</i> , MIC 3.125 to 25 µg/mL, MFC 6.25 to 25 µg/mL	Showed potent fungicidal activity against drug-resistant <i>C. auris</i> , with generally close MIC and MFC values	Basso et al. 2018
Crotamine	Venom of the South American rattlesnake <i>Crotalus durissus terrificus</i>	Cationic venom-derived antimicrobial peptide	Planktonic growth inhibition assay, approximately 50% growth inhibition for most strains at 0.2 to 0.4 µg/mL	Showed inhibition of multidrug-resistant <i>C. auris</i> isolates.	Colombo et al. 2019
Pom-1 and Pom-2	Freshwater snail <i>Pomacea poeyana</i>	Invertebrate antimicrobial peptides	Planktonic and biofilm assays, planktonic IC ₅₀ 8.4 to 8.5 µg/mL; biofilm IC ₅₀ 2.2 to 4.2 µg/mL	Showed moderate activity against planktonic <i>C. auris</i> cells, but stronger inhibition of de novo biofilm formation.	Raber et al. 2021
Dermaseptin	Frog skin secretion, <i>Phyllomedusa</i> spp.	Antimicrobial peptide, dermaseptin family	Planktonic MIC/MFC assays, MIC 7.81 to 15.62 µg/mL, MFC 15.62 to 31.25 µg/mL.	Showed reduction of 24 h mature <i>C. auris</i> biofilms by 33.1% at the MIC and 93.76% at the MFC and induced oxidative stress and dose-dependent apoptosis	Wani et al. 2024
Solenopsins	Venom of the red fire ant, <i>Solenopsis invicta</i>	Piperidine alkaloids	Planktonic assay, IC ₅₀ 0.7 to 1.4 µg/mL for natural and synthetic solenopsin mixtures; biofilm, combination, membrane integrity, and <i>in vivo</i> assays	Showed inhibition of planktonic growth of <i>C. auris</i> strains from different clades, reduced biofilm matrix deposition and metabolic activity, additive effects with amphotericin B, membrane disruption, and improved survival in infected <i>Galleria mellonella</i> larvae	Honorato et al. 2024

against *C. auris*. These peptides are particularly relevant because they operate at mucosal and epithelial surfaces, which are key sites for *Candida* colonization and biofilm development, and because their mechanisms of action differ fundamentally from those of azoles and echinocandins. Histatin 5, a human salivary peptide belonging to the histatin family, has been shown to exert potent candidacidal activity against *C. auris*, including fluconazole-resistant clinical isolates (Pathirana et al. 2018). Fungicidal activity was observed at 22.77 µg/mL and required peptide internalization, with translocation into the cytosol and vacuole preceding cell death, a mechanism previously described for *C. albicans*. Notably, azole resistance did not diminish susceptibility to histatin 5, indicating that its antifungal activity bypasses resistance pathways linked to ergosterol biosynthesis or drug efflux (Pathirana et al. 2018). These properties underscore the ability of innate peptides to target multidrug-resistant *C. auris* through mechanisms that remain effective despite conventional resistance determinants (Basso et al. 2018; Pathirana et al. 2018).

Primate θ-defensins, particularly rhesus θ-defensin-1 (RTD-1), represent an evolutionarily distinct subgroup of macrocyclic, cysteine-rich host-defense peptides. RTD-1 and related θ-defensins displayed rapid and pronounced fungicidal activity against multidrug-resistant *C. auris*, with reported potency comparable to, and in some cases exceeding, that of amphotericin B and caspofungin (Basso et al. 2018). Mechanistic studies demonstrated mem-

brane permeabilization, ATP release, and intracellular accumulation of reactive oxygen species, all occurring independently of mitochondrial ATP synthesis (Basso et al. 2018). An important distinguishing feature of θ-defensins is their high resistance to fungal proteases, a property that mitigates a common limitation of many linear antimicrobial peptides. Taken together, these characteristics support the value of θ-defensins as structural and mechanistic templates for antifungal drug design rather than as direct therapeutic agents (Basso et al. 2018).

Non-mammalian animal-derived peptides and alkaloids

A wide range of antimicrobial peptides and bioactive molecules derived from venomous and non-mammalian animals has been evaluated for activity against *C. auris*. These agents often combine strong membrane-disruptive activity with structural features absent from mammalian peptides, thereby expanding the chemical and mechanistic space available for antifungal discovery. Crotamine, a cationic peptide isolated from rattlesnake venom, demonstrated direct *in vitro* antifungal activity against *C. auris* as well as other multidrug-resistant *Candida* species, including isolates resistant to amphotericin B and fluconazole (Colombo et al. 2019). Antifungal effects were observed for most strains at 0.2 to 0.4 µg/mL, without detectable hemolytic activity under the tested conditions. As observed for many

venom-derived peptides, crothamine-mediated killing is primarily attributed to membrane-disruptive mechanisms, supporting its positioning as a structural lead rather than a fully developed therapeutic candidate (Colombo et al. 2019). Invertebrate-derived antimicrobial peptides have shown pronounced antibiofilm activity against *C. auris*. Pom-2, in particular, retained full efficacy against *C. auris* biofilms, highlighting a clear dissociation between planktonic antifungal potency and antibiofilm activity. This distinction emphasizes the importance of incorporating biofilm-specific endpoints when assessing antifungal candidates for *C. auris* and supports invertebrate peptides as promising scaffolds for antibiofilm-focused optimization (Dominguez et al. 2019; Raber et al. 2021). Dermaseptin, derived from the skin of the *Phyllomedusa* frog, exhibited fungicidal activity against *C. auris* at 7.81 to 15.62 µg/mL (Wani et al. 2024). Its antifungal effect was associated with marked oxidative stress, including increased lipid peroxidation, altered antioxidant enzyme activity and gene expression, and induction of dose-dependent apoptosis. These observations indicate that dermaseptin-mediated killing involves intracellular oxidative damage in addition to membrane perturbation, adding further mechanistic diversity to animal-derived antifungal peptides.

Animal-derived antifungal bioactives are not restricted to peptides. Solenopsins, piperidine alkaloids isolated from fire ant venom (*Solenopsis invicta*), represent a rare example of non-peptidic animal-derived antifungal agents (Honorato et al. 2024). Solenopsins inhibited both planktonic and biofilm-associated *C. auris*, including drug-resistant isolates, disrupted membrane integrity, and reduced biofilm matrix deposition (Honorato et al. 2024). Additive interactions with amphotericin B and demonstrated efficacy in a *Galleria mellonella* infection model further support their potential as antifungal leads or adjunctive agents. Fig. 3 summarizes representative small-molecule scaffolds discussed in Sections 3.1 to 3.3.

Pharmaceutical development strategies for anti-*Candida auris* natural products

Translation of natural products into viable therapeutic candidates for *C. auris* is often limited by insufficient potency or selectivity, chemical instability, and unfavorable physicochemical properties. Progress in this area has therefore relied on three complementary strategies: semisynthetic modification of natural scaffolds, rational combination with existing antifungal agents, and formulation or delivery approaches designed to improve stability and bioavailability. This section reviews natural-product-derived compounds, combination regimens, and formulation strategies that have shown experimentally demonstrated antifungal or antibiofilm activity against *C. auris*. The principal development pathways discussed are summarized in Fig. 4.

Figure 3. Representative small-molecule natural products from plant, microbial, and animal sources with reported activity against *C. auris*. (A) Plant-derived compounds. (B) Microbial-derived compounds. (C) Animal-derived solenopsin alkaloids.

Figure 4. Pharmaceutical development strategies for optimization of anti-*Candida auris* natural products.

Semisynthetic derivatives and natural-product-inspired scaffolds

Semisynthetic modification of natural antifungal scaffolds remains a central pharmaceutical strategy in drug discovery directed at multidrug-resistant *C. auris*. This approach is particularly important when native natural products are limited by poor solubility, instability, inadequate selectivity, or low bioavailability. Continued clinical dependence on azoles and echinocandins, together with the increasing prevalence of resistance-associated mutations, has exposed both the value and the limitations of existing natural-product-derived chemotypes. In *C. auris*, resistance is strongly associated with specific genetic alterations,

most notably mutations in *ERG11*, which encodes lanosterol 14 α -demethylase and confers azole resistance, and mutations in *FKS1*, which encodes the catalytic subunit of β -1,3-glucan synthase and confers echinocandin resistance (Hou et al. 2019). The repeated emergence of substitutions such as Y132F and K143R in *ERG11* and S639F within the *FKS1* hot-spot region underscores the need for scaffold innovation rather than incremental optimization. In this context, echinocandins provide a paradigmatic example of natural-product-derived scaffolds whose semisynthetic refinement enabled selective inhibition of fungal cell wall biosynthesis (Aldholmi et al. 2019). At the same time, the association between *FKS1* mutations and echinocandin resistance in *C. auris* illustrates the vulnerability of single-target strategies and reinforces the need to explore alternative natural-product-inspired scaffolds capable of circumventing established resistance mechanisms.

Polyene antibiotics remain relevant as candidates for scaffold diversification, despite limitations for systemic clinical use. Natamycin, a macrolide polyene with broad-spectrum antifungal activity and relatively low intrinsic toxicity, is limited by poor aqueous solubility and low bioavailability (Tevyashova et al. 2023). Therefore, semisynthetic modification of natamycin through amide formation has been shown to improve solubility and modulate membrane selectivity while preserving or enhancing antifungal activity against *Candida* species, including *C. auris* (Tevyashova et al. 2023). Selected derivatives exhibited favorable efficacy-to-toxicity profiles based on ergosterol versus cholesterol membrane interactions and mammalian cytotoxicity assays, supporting rational polyene scaffold modification as a viable route to antifungal leads with improved pharmaceutical properties and mechanisms distinct from those of azoles and echinocandins (Tevyashova et al. 2023).

Natural-product-inspired medicinal chemistry has also produced hybrid molecules designed to directly engage azole-relevant resistance pathways. Imidazole- and triazole-containing derivatives constructed around the phenylpropanoid scaffold of eugenol displayed antifungal activity against *Candida* species, including multidrug-resistant *C. auris* (Campos Péret et al. 2023). Experimental and computational analyses indicated disruption of ergosterol biosynthesis, consistent with interaction with *ERG11*-encoded lanosterol 14 α -demethylase, while molecular docking revealed binding modes comparable to those of established azole antifungals. These findings illustrate how natural-product scaffolds can be combined with azole pharmacophores to preserve target engagement while enabling structural diversification that may help address resistance-associated mutations. A related approach is exemplified by cinnamaldehyde-based azole derivatives, which integrate an electrophilic natural scaffold with azole functionality (Wani et al. 2022). A lead cinnamaldehyde-derived azole exhibited potent antifungal activity against virulent *C. auris* strains and induced fungal cell death through a multifactorial mechanism involving cell cycle arrest and suppression of oxidative stress

defenses (Wani et al. 2022). Inhibition of antioxidant enzyme expression and activity resulted in intracellular reactive oxygen species accumulation, suggesting that engagement of stress-response pathways may complement classical *ERG11*-associated mechanisms in azole-resistant phenotypes. Together, these studies show that semisynthetic modification and natural-product-inspired scaffold design remain productive approaches for antifungal lead discovery. By targeting resistance mechanisms associated with *ERG11* and *FKS1*, these strategies provide a rational pharmaceutical framework for developing next-generation antifungal agents against *C. auris*.

Combination strategies and synergistic interactions

Combination-based strategies constitute the most extensively investigated and mechanistically supported approach for enhancing the antifungal performance of natural products against *C. auris*. Given the intrinsic and acquired resistance of this pathogen to multiple antifungal classes, a substantial body of work has focused on using natural products as modulators that restore or potentiate the activity of existing drugs rather than as stand-alone agents.

Among quorum-sensing-derived molecules, farnesol is the most comprehensively characterized combination partner. In biofilm-associated models of *C. auris*, farnesol displayed consistent synergistic interactions with echinocandins, including anidulafungin, caspofungin, and micafungin, as demonstrated by checkerboard assays, Bliss independence analysis, and multiple complementary assessments of biofilm viability and architecture (Nagy et al. 2020). These interactions were supported by microscopy-based evidence of extensive biofilm damage, indicating relevance in sessile growth states that are typically refractory to antifungal therapy. Farnesol also enhanced fluconazole activity against azole-resistant *C. auris* isolates, reducing minimum inhibitory concentrations and altering resistance-associated pathways (Dekkerová et al. 2022). Mechanistic studies documented downregulation of *CDR1* and *ERG11*, inhibition of Cdr1-mediated efflux, and restoration of intracellular fluconazole accumulation, supporting a resistance-modifying role rather than direct fungicidal activity in this context (Dekkerová et al. 2022). Phenolic natural products have also been evaluated as combination partners with conventional antifungals. Carvacrol, a phenolic monoterpene, exhibited intrinsic antifungal activity against *C. auris* and showed synergistic or additive interactions with fluconazole, amphotericin B, nystatin, and caspofungin in a strain-dependent manner (Shaban et al. 2020). At subinhibitory concentrations, carvacrol reduced epithelial adherence and proteinase production, indicating that combination regimens may simultaneously attenuate virulence while enhancing antifungal efficacy (Shaban et al. 2020).

Essential oils and their derived fractions represent another prominent category of natural-product-based

combination strategies. *Cinnamomum verum* essential oil exhibited checkerboard-defined synergy with fluconazole at therapeutically relevant concentrations against *C. auris* (Di Vito et al. 2023). This interaction correlated with reduced fungal ATPase activity, increased intracellular accumulation of fluconazole, and restoration of fluconazole efficacy in a *Galleria mellonella* infection model, without detectable toxicity. Subsequent fractionation experiments demonstrated that formal synergy required the concurrent presence of multiple phytochemical constituents, specifically cinnamaldehyde, *o*-methoxycinnamaldehyde, and cinnamyl acetate (Di Vito et al. 2023). When evaluated individually, cinnamaldehyde produced only additive effects with fluconazole, despite restoring functional drug activity at concentrations similar to those of the complete phytochemical, underscoring the importance of multi-component composition in achieving true synergistic interactions (Di Vito et al. 2023).

Broader screening studies of chemically characterized essential oils combined with standard antifungals further illustrate the context-dependent nature of these interactions. Lemongrass, clove bud, and cinnamon bark essential oils produced synergistic, additive, indifferent, or antagonistic effects depending on the specific oil–drug pairing (Parker et al. 2022). Lemongrass oil showed synergy with selected antifungals. Clove bud oil showed synergy with fluconazole and flucytosine but antagonism with amphotericin B. Cinnamon bark oil did not show synergy under the tested conditions. Differences between these findings and previous reports of synergy for *Cinnamomum* oils may reflect variation in chemical definition, assay resolution, and evaluation strategy. Targeted studies by Di Vito and colleagues showed that synergy with fluconazole depends on precise phytochemical composition and concentration ratios. Preparations lacking this balance produced only additive or indifferent effects. In particular, checkerboard-defined synergy required the combined presence of cinnamaldehyde, *o*-methoxycinnamaldehyde, and cinnamyl acetate. Cinnamon oil preparations lacking this balanced composition did not reproduce that effect. Together, these findings indicate that synergy in essential-oil-based combinations is not a class-wide property but depends on precise chemical composition and experimental context.

Combination approaches are not restricted to intrinsically antifungal natural products. Paranazzamides A and B, cyclic dipeptides isolated from a reptile-associated fungal isolate, lacked direct antifungal activity against *C. auris* but enhanced amphotericin B efficacy in combination assays (Kobayashi et al. 2024). This finding supports the concept that certain natural products function primarily as drug-sensitizing or resistance-modulating agents.

Overall, natural-product-based combination strategies can enhance antifungal efficacy against *C. auris* through mechanisms that include efflux inhibition, metabolic interference, virulence attenuation, and biofilm disruption (Nagy et al. 2020; Shaban et al. 2020; Dekkerová et al. 2022; Di Vito et al. 2023). At the same time, variability

across compounds, partner drugs, and assay conditions highlights the importance of standardized evaluation frameworks and careful interpretation when extrapolating *in vitro* interaction data to therapeutic potential. Representative combination strategies evaluated against *C. auris* are summarized in Table 6.

Formulation strategies and delivery systems

Formulation-based approaches applied to natural products targeting *C. auris* have primarily focused on improving physicochemical stability, solubility, and delivery, rather than on increasing the intrinsic antifungal potency. This emphasis reflects the practical limitations of many natural products, particularly volatile or chemically labile agents such as essential oils, whose direct use is often constrained by rapid degradation, poor aqueous dispersibility, and variable bioavailability.

Liposomal encapsulation has been most extensively investigated using *Lavandula angustifolia* essential oil. In persister-enriched biofilm models of *C. auris*, liposome-encapsulated lavender oil inhibited planktonic growth and eradicated both primary and persister-derived biofilms at concentrations comparable to those required for the free oil (Alteriis et al. 2022). Mechanistic analyses linked antifungal activity to intracellular reactive oxygen species accumulation and transcriptional modulation of stress- and membrane-associated pathways, including downregulation of *ERG11* and *ALS5* and activation of *HOG1*. Encapsulation did not result in a measurable increase in antifungal potency but did improve oil stability and solubility, highlighting the role of liposomal systems as delivery-enabling platforms rather than potency-enhancing interventions (Alteriis et al. 2022). Nanostructured lipid carriers (NLCs) have also been employed to stabilize and deliver *Lippia sidoides* essential oil, a thymol-rich botanical preparation with established antifungal properties. NLC-loaded *L. sidoides* oil displayed *in vitro* antifungal activity against multidrug-resistant *C. auris* that was comparable to that of the free essential oil (Baldim et al. 2022). Assessment in a *Galleria mellonella* toxicity model revealed no detectable adverse effects, supporting the carrier system's biocompatibility. As observed with liposomal lavender oil, the principal benefit of NLC formulation lies in enhanced stability and controlled delivery. Polymer-based nanoparticle systems have been evaluated using *Cinnamomum cassia* essential oil formulated within polycaprolactone (PCL) nanoparticles. Nano-formulated *C. cassia* oil retained fungistatic and fungicidal activity against both planktonic and biofilm-associated *C. auris*, with antifungal performance similar to that of the non-encapsulated oil (Rosato et al. 2023). Checkerboard assays showed that nanoparticle formulation did not induce synergistic interactions with micafungin or fluconazole, reinforcing the conclusion that polymeric encapsulation primarily supports delivery and stability rather than altering pharmacodynamic interactions.

Table 6. Natural-product combinations evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Source of natural product	Chemical class	Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
Farnesol–echinocandin combinations	Fungal quorum-sensing metabolite, classically associated with <i>Candida albicans</i>	Sesquiterpenoid alcohol	Biofilm combination assays, FICI 0.133 to 0.507	Showed synergism in 11 of 12 tested combinations against <i>C. auris</i> biofilms, supported by LIVE/DEAD assay and scanning electron microscopy	Nagy et al. 2020
Farnesol–fluconazole combination	Fungal quorum-sensing metabolite, classically associated with <i>Candida albicans</i>	Sesquiterpenoid alcohol	Planktonic checkerboard assay, FIC index 0.4 to 0.75	Showed synergistic interaction with fluconazole, particularly in the resistant isolate, accompanied by significant <i>CDR1</i> downregulation, supporting modulation of azole resistance mechanisms	Dekkerová et al. 2022
Carvacrol–antifungal combinations	Representative plant sources include <i>Origanum vulgare</i> and <i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	Monoterpenoid phenol	Planktonic combination assays, carvacrol median MIC 125 µg/mL	Showed that carvacrol was the most active tested phenol, and its combination with fluconazole, amphotericin B, nystatin, and caspofungin produced synergistic or additive effects in 68%, 64%, 96%, and 28% of isolates, respectively, with additional effects on virulence factors	Shaban et al. 2020
<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> essential oil–fluconazole	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>	Phenylpropanoid-rich essential oil	Planktonic checkerboard assays, FIC 0.26 ± 0.14	Showed synergy with fluconazole, increased intracellular fluconazole accumulation, reduced ATPase activity, disrupted preformed biofilm, and improved survival in infected <i>Galleria mellonella</i> larvae	Di Vito et al. 2023
Active phytocomplex FR2 from <i>C. verum</i> oil–fluconazole	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>	Multicomponent phenylpropanoid mixture	Planktonic checkerboard assays, FIC 0.20 ± 0.12	Showed checkerboard-defined synergy comparable to the whole oil, supporting the contribution of phytocomplex composition rather than cinnamaldehyde alone	Di Vito et al. 2023
Cinnamaldehyde–fluconazole	Characteristic of <i>Cinnamomum verum</i> bark oil	Phenylpropanoid aldehyde	Planktonic checkerboard assays, FIC 0.52 ± 0.20	Showed additive activity, indicating that cinnamaldehyde alone did not reproduce the full synergistic effect of the whole oil or FR2	Di Vito et al. 2023
Clove bud oil–fluconazole/ flucytosine combinations	Clove bud essential oil from <i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Essential oil mixture	Planktonic checkerboard assays, FICI 0.1875 to 0.375	Showed synergistic interactions with fluconazole and flucytosine against <i>C. auris</i>	Parker et al. 2022
Paranannizziopsis A and B–amphotericin B	<i>Paranannizziopsis</i> sp. UH-21, reptile-associated fungal isolate	Prenylated cyclic dipeptides	Planktonic combination assay, no intrinsic activity up to 128 µg/mL; in combination, 4 to 64 µg/mL reduced amphotericin B MIC from 1.0 to 0.25 µg/mL	Showed no standalone antifungal activity but dose-dependent potentiation of amphotericin B against <i>C. auris</i> , with 2-to-4-fold enhancement at the highest tested concentrations	Kobayashi et al. 2024

Available evidence indicates that formulation-based strategies for natural products active against *C. auris* function mainly as enabling technologies that address formulation-related constraints, including volatility, instability, and delivery limitations. Although these systems improve experimental reproducibility and may enhance translational feasibility, they do not consistently increase intrinsic antifungal potency in their current form. Greater therapeutic impact is likely to be achieved by integrating formulation approaches with combination-based or resistance-modifying strategies, particularly for the management of multidrug-resistant and biofilm-associated *C. auris* infections. Representative formulation platforms and delivery strategies evaluated against *C. auris* are summarized in Table 7.

Discussion and future perspectives

Natural products continue to represent a valuable source of antifungal leads against *C. auris*, but their translational promise cannot be judged solely by potency and must instead be considered in light of model relevance, selectivity, safety, and the feasibility of development. Across plant-, microbial-, and animal-derived sources, diverse compounds and bioactive macromolecules have been reported to inhibit planktonic growth, interfere with biofilm formation, reduce virulence-associated traits, or enhance the activity of conventional antifungal drugs. Many of these effects appear to involve mechanisms that differ from

Table 7. Natural-product formulations evaluated against *Candida auris*.

Agent	Producing organism or source	Chemical class	Assay/potency	Key outcomes	Reference
Liposomal <i>Lavandula angustifolia</i> essential oil	<i>Lavandula angustifolia</i>	Terpenoid-rich essential oil and liposomal formulation	Planktonic and biofilm assays, significant planktonic growth reduction from 0.01% v/v; biofilm eradication >80% at 0.5% v/v	Showed eradication of both primary and persister-derived <i>C. auris</i> biofilms in a concentration-dependent manner; liposomes showed comparable antifungal efficacy to free oil while improving formulation stability and delivery	Alteriis et al. 2022
Nanostructured lipid carrier-loaded <i>Lippia sidoides</i> essential oil	<i>Lippia sidoides</i>	Thymol-rich essential oil, nanostructured lipid carrier formulation	Planktonic MIC/MFC assays and in vivo toxicity assays, MIC 0.281 to 0.563 µg/mL, MFC 0.281 to 1.125 µg/mL	Showed that EO-loaded nanostructured lipid carriers retained potent antifungal activity against multidrug-resistant <i>C. auris</i> and showed favorable biocompatibility and formulation stability	Baldim et al. 2022
Polycaprolactone nanoparticle-loaded <i>Cinnamomum cassia</i> essential oil	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i>	Phenylpropanoid-rich essential oil, polycaprolactone nanoparticle formulation	Planktonic MIC/MFC assays and biofilm disruption assays, MIC 0.01 ± 0.01 to $0.02 \pm 0.01\%$ v/v, MFC 0.01 ± 0.01 to $0.02 \pm 0.01\%$ v/v	Showed that free and nano-formulated oil had comparable fungistatic and fungicidal activity against <i>C. auris</i> and significantly disrupted preformed biofilm at 0.02% v/v; nanoencapsulation may support delivery and stability	Rosato et al. 2023

those of azoles and echinocandins, including membrane disruption, modulation of stress-response pathways, inhibition of efflux systems, interference with extracellular vesicle trafficking, and alteration of biofilm architecture (Zhang et al. 2020; Alteriis et al. 2022; Fatima et al. 2023; Honorato et al. 2024). At the same time, major questions remain regarding selectivity, safety, therapeutic window, and durability of response, particularly in the context of *C. auris*'s complex resistance phenotype. Accordingly, a critical interpretation of the available literature requires attention not only to antifungal activity but also to the extent to which these findings support progression toward clinically useful interventions.

Translational relevance and model limitations

A central challenge in interpreting the current literature is that many reported anti-*C. auris* effects are derived from *in vitro* assays or non-mammalian infection models, which are useful for early screening but do not reliably predict mammalian pharmacokinetics, tissue distribution, toxicity, or clinical efficacy (Jemel et al. 2020). This limitation is particularly important when evaluating compounds that appear highly active in planktonic or biofilm assays but have not been examined under conditions that reflect therapeutic exposure *in vivo*. Although models such as *Galleria mellonella* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* provide useful preliminary information on antifungal efficacy and toxicity, they cannot reproduce mammalian absorption, metabolism, organ distribution, or host–pathogen interactions at a clinically predictive level (Jemel et al. 2020). These constraints mean that many currently reported leads should still be regarded as preliminary candidates rather than validated therapeutic prospects.

Plant-derived natural products represent the largest group of reported agents, reflecting both the accessibility of botanical materials and the long-standing role of plants

in antifungal discovery. Within this category, chemically defined small molecules such as naphthoquinones, phenolic monoterpenoids, and selected tannins provide the clearest structure–activity signals (Marquez et al. 2023; de Moraes et al. 2024; Ríos-López et al. 2024; Jin and Eom 2025; Sousa et al. 2025a). By contrast, complex botanical preparations, including essential oils and other multi-component extracts, often show antifungal or antibiofilm effects but pose clear challenges for pharmaceutical development (Aldholmi et al. 2019; Tran et al. 2020; Ribeiro et al. 2022; Rosato et al. 2023; Machado et al. 2025). Their chemical heterogeneity, batch-to-batch variability, and limited selectivity complicate standardization, reproducibility, and safety assessment. For this reason, many plant-derived complex mixtures may be more realistic candidates for topical use, environmental decontamination, or device-associated applications than for systemic antifungal therapy.

Microbial-derived natural products, although fewer in number, appear especially promising because they more often combine potency with mechanistic specificity (Zhang et al. 2020; Kovács et al. 2021; Singh et al. 2024b; Usui et al. 2025). Secondary metabolites, lipopeptides, antifungal proteins, and postbiotic preparations derived from bacteria and fungi frequently show defined targets or activity in biofilm and *in vivo* infection models. From a biosynthetic perspective, the available evidence remains uneven. Terpenoids, lipopeptides, proteins, postbiotic metabolites, and type I polyketide-derived scaffolds dominate the current literature, whereas highly oxidized aromatic type II polyketides remain largely unexplored. Turbinmicin is a notable exception and highlights the potential of this biosynthetic space as a source of antifungal activity against *C. auris*. This imbalance suggests that genome mining, metagenomics, and microbiome-guided discovery may uncover additional compounds that target biofilm integrity or vesicle-mediated processes rather than acting only through direct fungicidal effects.

Animal-derived antimicrobial peptides and peptide-inspired bioactives occupy a distinct place in the current antifungal landscape. Their rapid fungicidal effects, relative insensitivity to conventional resistance mechanisms, and marked antibiofilm activity make them attractive candidates for localized or adjunctive use. However, limitations related to stability, toxicity, immunogenicity, and large-scale production continue to restrict their development, especially for systemic therapy. Future progress in this area will likely depend on peptide engineering, improved delivery strategies, and the development of non-peptidic mimetics or hybrid molecules with more favorable pharmacological properties. In this respect, animal-derived molecules may be valuable not only as therapeutic candidates but also as structural and mechanistic templates for antifungal design.

Comparative efficacy, selectivity, and safety

The current research landscape is marked by significant heterogeneity across chemical classes, biological sources, and experimental methodologies. The reported potency data show that the most extensively studied biological source is not necessarily the one that provides the strongest lead compounds. Plant-derived natural products show the greatest variability in activity. At the high-potency end, ellagic acid was reported with MIC values of 0.125 to 0.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, although this unusually strong activity should be interpreted cautiously until confirmed by additional studies (Rossatto et al. 2021). Plumbagin also showed relatively strong activity, with MIC values of 1–4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and marked antibiofilm effects (Jin and Eom 2025). By contrast, other plant-derived agents, such as carvacrol and geraniol, were active only at substantially higher concentrations, in the ranges of 125 to 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 225 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, respectively (Ismail et al. 2022; Fatima et al. 2023). Among essential oils, potent activity was reported for *Cinnamomum verum* bark oil and *Cinnamomum cassia* oil, although these data are not directly comparable with MIC values reported for purified compounds because they were expressed as % *v/v* rather than $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ (Tran et al. 2020; Rosato et al. 2023). Despite the apparent potency of some plant-derived leads, selectivity remains a major concern. Cinnamaldehyde, for example, showed fungicidal activity against *C. auris*, but cytotoxicity was also detected at active concentrations, indicating a narrow therapeutic window (Sousa et al. 2025a). In contrast, eugenol exhibited fungicidal activity without detectable cytotoxicity at growth-inhibitory concentrations, suggesting a more favorable preliminary selectivity profile (Sousa et al. 2025a). Plumbagin should also be interpreted cautiously as a lead compound. Although its antifungal activity was strong, quinone scaffolds are often associated with broad redox reactivity and possible host-cell toxicity, which may complicate drug development (Jin and Eom 2025).

Microbial-derived natural products include some of the strongest translational leads. Turbinmicin showed

MIC values as low as 0.25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ against a pan-resistant *C. auris* strain, lacked detectable hemolytic activity at the tested concentrations, and reduced kidney fungal burden in a neutropenic mouse model, making it one of the most compelling candidates reported to date (Zhang et al. 2020). Other microbial agents, such as guanacastepene V, dahliane C, and the bacillomycin-class lipopeptide AF4, also showed relatively strong *in vitro* activity, but the latter was associated with substantial mammalian cytotoxicity and hemolysis at suprainhibitory concentrations (Usui et al. 2025; Ramachandran et al. 2018). Compound 55B3 is notable for combining antifungal and antibiofilm activity with no detectable cytotoxicity in HepG2 cells, although its potency remained lower than that of turbinmicin (Singh et al. 2024b).

Animal-derived peptides occupy an intermediate position in this landscape. Several showed strong antifungal or antibiofilm effects, particularly θ -defensins and the Pom peptides, with MIC or IC_{50} values in the low-to-mid $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ range (Basso et al. 2018; Raber et al. 2021). However, not all peptide-based agents were equally potent. Dermaseptin, for example, required $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentrations despite substantial biofilm reduction at higher exposure levels (Wani et al. 2024). These findings suggest that animal-derived antifungal peptides may be especially valuable for topical, device-associated, or adjunctive applications, where rapid membrane-active effects and antibiofilm properties are advantageous, but systemic development remains limited by stability, delivery, and toxicity considerations (Basso et al. 2018; Colombo et al. 2019; Wani et al. 2024).

Overall, these findings suggest that plant-derived products provide the greatest chemical diversity (Rossatto et al. 2021; de Moraes et al. 2024; Sousa et al. 2025a), microbial-derived metabolites currently offer the strongest potency-driven leads (Zhang et al. 2020; Singh et al. 2024b; Usui et al. 2025), and animal-derived molecules appear especially relevant for membrane-active and antibiofilm strategies (Raber et al. 2021; Honorato et al. 2024; Wani et al. 2024). Microbial-derived metabolites, especially those with defined molecular targets or demonstrated *in vivo* efficacy, offer the greatest translational potential, whereas plant- and animal-derived agents, although often more limited in direct pharmaceutical applicability, continue to provide valuable structural diversity and mechanistic insights that inform antifungal discovery and design. These comparisons should nevertheless be interpreted cautiously, because reported potency depends strongly on assay conditions, strain background, endpoint definition, and whether the tested material was a purified compound, peptide, fraction, or complex extract. Moreover, potency alone should not be interpreted as evidence of therapeutic promise, because selectivity and safety remain major unresolved limitations across much of the current literature. For several quinones, phenylpropanoids, and essential-oil constituents, antifungal effects are observed at concentrations that may overlap with cytotoxic, irritant, or membrane-active effects in mammalian systems (Ramachan-

dran et al. 2018; Jin and Eom 2025; Sousa et al. 2025a). This concern is especially relevant for chemically reactive or broadly membrane-perturbing compounds, where fungicidal activity may reflect limited pathogen selectivity rather than a favorable therapeutic window (Ramachandran et al. 2018). By contrast, only a smaller subset of candidates, such as eugenol under the tested conditions, D-lp1, compound 55B3, and turbinmicin, was accompanied by data suggestive of at least preliminary selectivity or tolerability (Zhang et al. 2020; Kamli et al. 2022; Singh et al. 2024b; Sousa et al. 2025a). Even in these cases, the available evidence remains heterogeneous and incomplete, since cytotoxicity, hemolysis, and *in vivo* tolerability were not assessed using standardized designs across studies. While only a limited number of candidates currently exhibit the potency, selectivity, and pharmacokinetic profiles necessary for standalone systemic therapy, many natural products display clinically relevant effects that address the multifactorial challenges posed by this pathogen. These effects include disruption of biofilm architecture, attenuation of virulence-associated traits, circumvention of established resistance mechanisms, and enhanced efficacy of existing antifungal drugs. Accordingly, future work should place greater emphasis on reporting mammalian cytotoxicity alongside antifungal potency and, where possible, on calculating a comparable selectivity index to distinguish general bioactivity from compounds with a realistic therapeutic window.

Future directions

Among the strategies examined, combination-based approaches appear to offer the most immediate practical value. Many natural products seem to function more effectively as resistance-modifying agents that restore or enhance the activity of azoles, echinocandins, or polyenes than as standalone antifungals (Nagy et al. 2020; Kovács et al. 2021; Dekkerová et al. 2022; Di Vito et al. 2023). This appears particularly relevant in biofilm-associated models, which better reflect the clinical behavior of *C. auris* infections (Dominguez et al. 2019; Romera et al. 2019; Nagy et al. 2020; Kovács et al. 2021). At the same time, variability in reported outcomes across compounds, partner drugs, and assay designs highlights the need for standardized combination testing and careful interpretation of interaction data. It is important to distinguish true synergy from additive effects or functional re-sensitization, especially when evaluating multicomponent natural products. Such properties underscore the translational potential of natural products as adjunctive therapies or as components of combination regimens, even if they are not yet suitable as standalone systemic agents. Combination strategies and resistance-modifying effects therefore represent particularly promising avenues for achieving near-term clinical relevance, especially in the context of biofilm-associated and drug-refractory infections. Formulation-based strategies address a different issue, namely the distinction between improving delivery

and increasing intrinsic antifungal potency. Liposomal systems, lipid carriers, and polymeric nanoparticles have generally improved stability, solubility, and experimental reproducibility, but they have not consistently increased antifungal activity on their own (Alteriis et al. 2022; Baldim et al. 2022; Rosato et al. 2023). Their main value lies in enabling more reliable delivery of chemically labile or poorly soluble compounds. Greater therapeutic benefit is therefore more likely when formulation approaches are integrated with combination strategies rather than treated as a standalone solution.

Looking ahead, several priorities emerge for advancing natural-product-based antifungal research against *C. auris*. These include broader use of biosynthetically informed discovery strategies, greater emphasis on antibiofilm and persistence-related endpoints, improved chemical standardization of complex natural products, and wider adoption of clinically relevant infection and colonization models. A particularly important next step is the medicinal-chemistry optimization of active but pharmacologically limited natural scaffolds, especially quinones, for which semisynthetic derivatization may improve solubility, membrane selectivity, and overall developability (Aldholmi et al. 2019; de Moraes et al. 2024; Jin and Eom 2025). Future studies should also prioritize systematic evaluation of combination therapies in models that better reflect device-associated, mucosal, and persistent infections. Greater impact is expected from the strategic integration of natural product chemistry with combination therapy, formulation science, and biosynthetically informed discovery approaches.

Conclusion

Overall, the literature reviewed here indicates that natural products remain a diverse and mechanistically valuable source of antifungal leads against *C. auris*. Their significance lies not only in direct antifungal activity but also in their capacity to interfere with biofilm-associated behavior, modulate resistance-related phenotypes, and enhance the activity of existing antifungal agents. Collectively, these findings show that the contribution of natural products to *C. auris* research extends beyond the search for standalone antifungal agents and includes their broader value as scaffolds for optimization, sources of mechanistic insight, and components of adjunctive or combination-based strategies. At the same time, the available evidence remains uneven, and only a limited number of candidates appear sufficiently developed for further translational consideration. Future progress will depend on stronger integration of rigorous chemical characterization, translationally relevant biological models, medicinal optimization, and rational combination strategies. Within this framework, natural products should be viewed not simply as isolated bioactive molecules but as a continuing source of scaffolds, mechanisms, and adjunctive approaches for antifungal development against *C. auris*.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article and its supplementary material.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary table

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Data type: docx

Explanation note: **table S1.** Search strategies used for literature retrieval. **table S2.** Expanded list of plant-derived natural products, extracts, essential oils, and complex matrices evaluated against *Candida auris*.

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